

A NEW ROUTE TO POLYCYCLIC COMPOUNDS HAVING ANGULAR METHYL GROUP. SYNTHESIS OF ISOCHRYSOFLUOREN

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The synthesis of isochrysofluoren is described.

Many important complex terpenes, the sterols and certain of the alkaloids are stated to have an alkyl group attached to a carbon atom which is itself a common member of two ring systems. Synthesis of such complex bodies will only be possible by a process which will ultimately lead to a compound having angular methyl group. Investigation described below was undertaken with a view to developing one such method.

α -Naphthyl magnesium bromide is allowed to react with ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate to yield ethyl 1- α -naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexanol-2-carboxylate (I). This on dehydration yields ethyl 1- α -naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexene-2-carboxylate (II). This unsaturated ester is reduced catalytically (Roger-Adam's platinum oxide catalyst) to yield ethyl 1- α -naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexane-2-carboxylate (III). 1- α -Naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexane-2-carboxylic acid, obtained after hydrolysis of the ester (III), is converted into acid chloride by the action of thionyl chloride and subjected to the action of aluminium chloride to yield methylhexahydroperibenanthron (IV). This derivative is reduced by means of phosphorus and hydriodic acid when methylhexahydroisochrysofluoren (V) is obtained. The compound (V), when heated with selenium, yields isochrysofluoren (VI).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-methyl-2-carboxylate.—Methylation of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate by the method of Kotz and Michels (*Annalen*, 1905, 360, 210) was found to be unsatisfactory as by this method, a substance free from ferric chloride colouration was never obtained. Chung, Tien Huang (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 164) using sodium methoxide in methyl alcoholic solution obtained the methylated compound in somewhat better yield. But by the following method a product was obtained which gave no colouration with ferric chloride and the yield was almost quantitative.

A mixture of sodium (5 g.), benzene (250 c.c.) and ethyl cyclohexanone 2-carboxylate (34 g.) was left overnight. The sodium salt, which separated, was then refluxed with methyl iodide (18 c.c.) for 4 hours on the water-bath and worked up in the usual manner, b.p. 104-105°/6-7 mm.

Ethyl 1- α -Naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexanol-2-carboxylate (I).—When an ethereal solution of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-methyl-2-carboxylate (15 g.) was treated with α -naphthyl magnesium bromide (from 12 c.c. of α -bromonaphthalene and 1.9 g. of magnesium) a gelatinous precipitate separated. The mixture was left overnight and decomposed with cold dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed several times with water, and the product distilled at 220-25°/6 mm. as a viscous liquid. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 7.8. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 76.9; H, 7.69 per cent).

Ethyl 1- α -Naphthyl-2-methylcyclohexane-2-carboxylate (II).—A mixture of ethyl-1- α -naphthyl-2-methyl-2-carboxycyclohexanol (41 g.) and pyridine (22.8 c.c.) in ether (83 c.c.) was cooled in an ice-bath and thionyl chloride (10 c.c.) was added drop by drop with constant shaking. It was then left at ordinary temperature for 2 hours. The ethereal layer was separated after addition of ice-water, washed successively with cold dilute sulphuric acid, cold dilute caustic potash and water. After drying the ether was evaporated and the product was repeatedly distilled in vacuum and the portion coming at 210-20°/6 mm. was collected. (Found: C, 81.1; H, 7.4. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 81.6; H, 7.4 per cent).

Ethyl 1- α -Naphthyl 2-methylcyclohexane-2-carboxylate (III).—Freshly distilled unsaturated ester (II) (11 g.) was shaken in an alcoholic solution with platinum oxide (3 g.) for about one month when the calculated quantity of hydrogen was absorbed. The product after working up in the usual manner was distilled, b. p. 208-10°/6 mm. (Found: C, 81.5; H, 8.2. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 81.08; H, 8.1 per cent).

1- α -Naphthyl-2-Methylcyclohexane-2-carboxylic Acid.—The above ester was refluxed with three times the calculated quantity of alcoholic potash (10%) in a water-bath for 2 hours. Alcohol was removed after dilution, acidified, and the acid extracted with ether. The acid was removed from the ether extract by treating with sodium bicarbonate solution. On acidification the free acid was liberated. It was extracted with ether, dried with sodium sulphate, and the solvent removed, b. p. 235-45°/7 mm. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 7.3. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 80.6; H, 7.4 per cent).

Methylhexahydro- α -peri-benzanthron (IV).—The above acid (15 g.) was converted into its chloride by boiling for 3 hours with thionyl chloride (100 c.c.), excess of thionyl chloride being then removed on the water-bath under reduced pressure. An ice-cold carbon disulphide (100 c.c.) solution of the chloride was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.), kept at 0° for 3 hours, and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. After being washed with sodium carbonate solution it was dried, carbon disulphide removed and the residue distilled, b. p. 215-25°/4 mm. (Found: C, 87.0; H, 6.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires C, 86.4; H, 7.2 per cent).

isoChrysofluoren (VI).—The above ketone (2 g.), hydriodic acid (5 c.c., 50%) and red phosphorus (2 g.) were heated together for 8 to 10 hours under reflux. The product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water and dilute alkali. On removing ether a gummy residue was left, which was heated with selenium for 30 hours at 300-40° and the product was converted into picrate, m.p. 110-11°. *isoChrysofluoren*, regenerated from pure picrate, melted at 84° (lit. m.p. 84°, cf. Bally and Scholl, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1656). (Found: C, 94.8; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}$: C, 94.4; H, 5.5 per cent).